

Funding and Sustainability Event

Organised by UK TRE community, January 28th 2025

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Working Group Survey Summary:

The working group's aims were to investigate using a survey of UK TRE organisations:

1. Cost/charging remits for different organisations
2. Cost categories and costing models being used
3. Where is funding coming from?
4. Monetisation / extra revenue stream ideas

And at this event the summary of the survey data (13 total respondents) was presented. The key summary points are:

1. There is little evidence of commercialisation at present, with **clear difference between NHS and Academia:**
 - The NHS is expecting to recover full costs
 - Whilst academia is not expecting self-sustainability and will provide 'core' support.
- 4/5 NHS organisations that completed the survey were expected to be financial sustainable and 1 had to meet part of their costs.
- Of the academic organisations, 4/5 were expected to cover some of their costs and 1 was funded by their institution. No academic institutions needed to cover costs completely.
- Of the 3 non-profits, 1 had to be fully financially sustainable, 1 had to meet some their costs and 1 was fully funded by their org

Costs:

- 7/13 organisations knew what their annual costs were and provided an estimate of **between £90k and £4m**. Estimates varied as some covered annual cost of infrastructure + staff and others the baseline infrastructure only.
- 5/13 did not know the annual cost of running their TRE. The majority of these were either in the process of setting up their TRE/service or had been open only a short time.

Charging: Respondents outlined what was charged for (see Figure 1) showing heterogeneity.

Data	Access to/delivery of the data	Technical eg compute, storage, workspaces	Consultancy & analysis	Project management	Technical Support	Feasibility requests	Operational/governance	Don't charge
	X	X		X				
		X		X	X			
								X
								X
X	X	X	X				X	
	X	X	X	X	X		X	
X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
		X			X		X	
X	X							
X			X					
	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	X	X						
		X		X	X		X	

Figure 1 What is charged for (one row represents a respondent)

- 6/11 organisations received most of their funding from academic research grants.
- 5/11 were mainly funded internally or by non-profit organisations.
- Only one mentioned commercial funding (from Pharma).
 - About half had details of charging model on their websites - others explained that costs were so variable that they were calculated on a project-by-project basis.
 - The majority had differential pricing for commercial and non-commercial customers (commercial companies paid more) and only two charged for data.

The National Data for R&D NHS programme:

Clare Pepper (Lead for the Commercial and Operating model for the NHS Research SDE Network) presented the approach to charging and sustainability developed within the England NHS programme. There were three service components (see Figure 2)

Data for R&D
PROGRAMME

What is an SDE service?

Across the NHS Research SDE Network, we have three service components:

Figure 2: Data for R&D programme service model

A number of principles were defined see Figure 3:

Core commercial principles and approach

Context

We are seeking to address the fragmented ecosystem with variable pricing, different contractual processes, complexity and extended timelines for access.

Principles

1. Pricing, as part of a broader commercial and contracting approach, must be harmonised across the SDE Research Network to provide user-consistency, enable federation and ensure sustainability
2. As a minimum, each project must recover its own costs
3. Pricing approach aligns to the Value Sharing Framework
4. **Development of pricing approach must be staged, building on user feedback and the maturity of SDEs**

Approach

1. A standard Data Access Agreement will be implemented across the NHS Research SDE Network for ease of contracting; single project and framework variants
2. The value of data will be determined and differentiated based on the nature of the project in which it's being used rather than the user
3. *Where applicable*, we will seek a share of the value derived from the use of NHS data assets.
4. Value return options are flexible for users both in terms of timing, method and risk management

Figure 3: Principles and approach for England Data for R&D programme

The set of service components and the total costs are shown in Figure 4. Clare presented a set of common questions asked

NHS Research SDE Network: Pricing Model

- Data access constructed of core Platform as a Service costs with discretionary Consultancy as a Service based on customer need.

Figure 4: Service cost component hierarchy model

This material prompted considerable questions and discussion – see [YouTube video](#)¹ to follow this in full.

The Context and overall picture

To present a wide view of Funding and Sustainability, and to prompt discussion, Pete Barnsley (The Francis Crick Institute) gave an overview set of slides (some copied below) that addressed:

- The Landscape today - duplicative TRE models and a spectrum of problems.
- The time-to-research being the economic driver based on UKRI funding analysis (see Figure 5)
- The funding models all reply on Tax Payer sources across four domains: Operational Zone / Data Zone / Research Zone / Research Organisation (RPO) Zone. See Figure 6

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dz-ZqseE7aM>

- A model of costs in a TRE / SDE (see Figure 7)
- The characteristics of these costs and drivers – Data Zone is very different to Research Zone, see Figure 8.
- A product model involving four key services central to the success of the eco-system: Data Collection, Preparation and Curation; Flexible secure scalable computing services; Information Governance; and Research data Discovery and design of experiments service. The latter being a weaker service offering.

Projects Today and Spending

- With the time-to-research (between gaining grant funding to having access to data and infrastructure) being ~1.5 years, this equates to 40-50% of a funded project's duration.

- Take Away:
- Shortening time-to-research can release a step change in value-for-money from UKRI investments
 - We can get more value if we sort the end-end, whole system problem.
 - Need to decide technology strategy based on whole system cost NOT cost per GigaFLOPs or Terabyte.
 - Strategy: Keep more money 'in the system' allowing for sustainable career and skills development.
- Data extracted from Gateway to Research: <https://gtr.ukri.org> 11/10/2023

Figure 5: Analysis of UKRI funding data: The dominant economic driver is the return from addressing the "time to research" delay across grants and PhDs.

Figure 6: Schematic Funding model illustrating the complexity and common Tax Payer source.

- **Standardise on specific “TRE” service products** across the whole community / landscape making comparison easy.
 - Use a tiered pricing model, the design of which is underpinned at highest policy level, to maximise data use (and so progress for society).
- There is **too much to be done, we need to grow the community**. But we need to **adjust the positions we play** to form a better team.

Figure 9: A proposal for funding- Align and balance the funding to optimise the gold arrow connecting the pipeline of research.

Discussion:

There followed almost an hour of engaged discussion using both Zoom chat and also comment and debate verbally. Watch the [YouTube video](#)² to follow this in full.

This debate centred on a few core things;

- The community discussion quickly **adopted federation as a “need to do”** operating model for the UK.
 - both the technical ability to do so, and
 - strategic importance of doing so
 - But the existing NHS funding solutions is put under hard tension with such a federated model.
 - Everything needs to have **federation aligned designs**: Information Governance / Technology / Funding etc.
 - **This is not happening**. An indicative option is here along with this funding picture.
- There was **no focus on funding the success of the end-end data eco-system**:
 - Operations → Data Zone → Research Zone → Researcher (RPO) zone (and then on back into Operations). See Figure 9
 - We are not yet acknowledging the costing / funding difference between a Data Zone and Research Zone “SDE/TRE”. See Figure 8.

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dz-ZqseE7aM>

- Based on a set of three online questions presented to the audience: the community overwhelmingly supported:
 - Continuation of the working group (97% of 36)
 - Work on a national (UK wide) funding strategy. (91% of 35)
 - The mid June half day community event should focus on Finance and Sustainability. (90% of 29): E.g. How do we (transfer) charge across a federated network?